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INSURANCE OF RURAL AGRIBUSINESS: CURRENT CHALLENGES AND FUTURE DEVELOPMENT

ESG-
(remote loss assessment),
, ESG,

The article explores insurance as a key mechanism for the financial resilience of rural agribusiness. It substantiates the interdependence between the insurance market, agricultural policy, and investment cycles in rural economies. Theoretical foundations, risk structure, and coverage architecture are examined, including index and parametric products, mutual/cooperative schemes, reinsurance, and public co-funding models. Market barriers are identified: low insurance literacy and trust, information asymmetry and moral hazard, insufficient actuarial data quality, weak capitalization and risk accumulation, regulatory fragmentation, claims-handling frictions, and climate change impacts. International experience informs a modernization agenda: climate stress-testing, data infrastructure and satellite monitoring, standardization of index/ESG-linked products, hybrid risk-sharing with governments and reinsurers, digital claims (remote loss assessment), expansion of cooperative and microinsurance, and integration with lending and PPPs. The article concludes that an ecosystem approach—data-driven, prevention-oriented, and long-term financed — is required.

Keywords: agricultural insurance, rural agribusiness, climate risk, parametric insurance, yield index, reinsurance, mutual insurance, premium subsidies, ESG, digital claims.

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ESG-

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ESG-

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(CAP).

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(MPCI).

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ESG-

ESG-

20

50-60 %

XXI

2050

2030

ESG-

ESG-

9

FAO,

2050

60-70%.

XXI

1. Dad'kov, V. N. Formirovanie otraslevykh sistem vzaimnogo strahovaniya i perspektivy ih razvitiya : special'nost' 08.00.10 «Finansy, denezhnoe obrashchenie i kredit» : dissertatsiya na soiskanie uchenoj stepeni doktora ekonomicheskikh nauk / Dad'kov Viktor Nikolaevich. — Moskva, 2007. — 395 s. — EDN QDZZOV.
2. Zolotar', A. A. Istoriya vznikoveniya i razvitiya strahovaniya v Rossii i zarubezhnykh stranah / A. A. Zolotar' // Ekonomika i sotsium. — 2015. — 1-3(14). — S. 266-271. — EDN UBGYRV.
3. Kalafatov, E. A. Osobennosti ispol'zovaniya investitsionnykh instrumentov v razvitiiterritorial'no-proizvodstvennykh kompleksov kak faktor razvitiya sel'skikh territorij / E. A. Kalafatov // Innovatsii i investitsii. — 2025. — 3. — S. 377-379. — EDN GBKUIZ.
4. Mart'nova, N. A. Problemy strahovaniya v sovremennom agropromyshlennom komplekse / N. A. Mart'nova // Vestnik Akademii prava i upravleniya. — 2019. — 3(56). — S. 97-102. — EDN NLNMCI.
5. Mash'yanova, E. E. Agrostrahovanie: problemy i perspektivy v Rossijskoj Federacii / E. E. Mash'yanova // Chronos. — 2019. — 7(34). — S. 49-56. — EDN DAUBHY.
6. Suhenko, V. A. Strahovanie agropromyshlennogo kompleksa v Rossii: sovremennoe sostoyanie i perspektivy razvitiya / V. A. Suhenko, K. A. Pugina // Nauchno-metodicheskij elektronnyj zhurnal «Koncept». — 2017. — T39. — S. 3996-4000. — EDN ZBGTSZ.
7. Vol'vak, Yu. S. Zarubezhnyj opyt agrostrahovaniya / Yu. S. Vol'vak // Vestnik Luganskogo gosudarstvennogo universiteta imeni Vladimira Dalja. — 2022. — 4(58). — S. 36-40. — EDN OSPYAI.
8. Shcherbakov, V. Rossijskij agrarnyj sektor v ozhidanii effektivnogo mekhanizma strahovaniya sel'skohozyajstvennykh riskov / V. Shcherbakov, I. Hominich // Rossijskij ekonomicheskij zhurnal. — 2010. — 4. — S. 104-107. — EDN PIECCN.

SPISOK LITERATURY

1. Dad'kov, V. N. Formirovanie otraslevykh sistem vzaimnogo strahovaniya i perspektivy ih razvitiya : special'nost' 08.00.10 «Finansy, denezhnoe obrashchenie i kredit» : dissertatsiya na soiskanie uchenoj stepeni doktora ekonomicheskikh nauk / Dad'kov Viktor Nikolaevich. — Moskva, 2007. — 395 s. — EDN QDZZOV.
2. Zolotar', A. A. Istoriya vznikoveniya i razvitiya strahovaniya v Rossii i zarubezhnykh stranah / A. A. Zolotar' // Ekonomika i sotsium. — 2015. — 1-3(14). — S. 266-271. — EDN UBGYRV.
3. Kalafatov, E. A. Osobennosti ispol'zovaniya investitsionnykh instrumentov v razvitiiterritorial'no-proizvodstvennykh kompleksov kak faktor razvitiya sel'skikh territorij / E. A. Kalafatov // Innovatsii i investitsii. — 2025. — 3. — S. 377-379. — EDN GBKUIZ.
4. Mart'nova, N. A. Problemy strahovaniya v sovremennom agropromyshlennom komplekse / N. A. Mart'nova // Vestnik Akademii prava i upravleniya. — 2019. — 3(56). — S. 97-102. — EDN NLNMCI.
5. Mash'yanova, E. E. Agrostrahovanie: problemy i perspektivy v Rossijskoj Federacii / E. E. Mash'yanova // Chronos. — 2019. — 7(34). — S. 49-56. — EDN DAUBHY.
6. Suhenko, V. A. Strahovanie agropromyshlennogo kompleksa v Rossii: sovremennoe sostoyanie i perspektivy razvitiya / V. A. Suhenko, K. A. Pugina // Nauchno-metodicheskij elektronnyj zhurnal «Koncept». — 2017. — T39. — S. 3996-4000. — EDN ZBGTSZ.
7. Vol'vak, Yu. S. Zarubezhnyj opyt agrostrahovaniya / Yu. S. Vol'vak // Vestnik Luganskogo gosudarstvennogo universiteta imeni Vladimira Dalja. — 2022. — 4(58). — S. 36-40. — EDN OSPYAI.
8. Shcherbakov, V. Rossijskij agrarnyj sektor v ozhidanii effektivnogo mekhanizma strahovaniya sel'skohozyajstvennykh riskov / V. Shcherbakov, I. Hominich // Rossijskij ekonomicheskij zhurnal. — 2010. — 4. — S. 104-107. — EDN PIECCN.

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